

Designing and Development of Strategies for Development of School Sports Olympiad in Kurdistan Province

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Abstract

The current research aims to design and develop the strategies for development of school sports Olympiad for Deputy of physical education and health of Ministry of Education in Kurdistan Province. Statistical sample were 30 of physical education teachers that were selected purposefully. The research tool was item-survey and three steps Delphi reciprocating technique. In order to analyze the research data, internal and external factors evaluation matrix were used in addition to descriptive indicators. The results of internal and external factors evaluation matrix showed that in terms of strategic situation, the Olympiad was in the area of strengths in terms of internal factors and was in the threats area in terms of external factors. Therefore, strategic situation of holding the Olympiad was calculated in ST point. Accordingly, “competitive strategies” have been recommended for school sports Olympiad. Hence, utilization of recognized strengths can help significantly to commit its prophecy and obligations provided that they will be used in accordance to minimizing the internal weaknesses and reduction of external threats and maximum usage of external opportunities.

Keywords: Competitive strategies, Olympiad, School, Strategy, SWOT

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